

Development Program, introduced the 2526 strain from Malaysia in 1973. Because the line was heterogeneous, it was further selected at Suakoko for adaptability and uniformity. The released population of Suakoko 8 is fairly uniform, photoperiod insensitive, and matures in about 140 days. It has good seedling vigor; good tillering ability; semicompact plant type; intermediate culms of intermediate diameter;

intermediate senescence; well-exserted, long, and heavy panicles; glabrous, pale green, and intermediate leaves; and erect flag leaves. Its grains are long, slender, and translucent. It suffers less damage than IR5 from the important diseases such as blast, sheath rot, sheath blight, leaf scald, and brown spot, as well as caseworm. Because it is photoperiod insensitive, Suakoko 8 is also superior to Gissi 27. Its plant type is well suited to

Liberian peasant farm conditions of imperfect water control, moderate fertilization, and manual harvesting.

During the 1977 wet season, Suakoko 8 seed were distributed for minikit and production kit trials. Seed is expected to reach a large number of farmers for planting in the 1978 wet season. **W**

India's national gene bank in international cooperation

J. K. Roy and A. Ashok Rao, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-6, India

The national rice germ plasm bank of India is maintained at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. The collection started with about 2,000 varieties obtained from the paddy breeding station, Coimbatore, in 1946–47. It gradually increased as varieties were obtained from different

states and abroad by request and exchange. About 10,000 additional varieties were added from systematic surveys from Jeypore tract of Orissa (1955–59); Manipur state (1965–70); northeastern India (Assam Rice Collection, 1968–71); and new collections, mostly from upland and rainfed tracts of nine states (1976–77). The national gene bank at present consists of 14,905 varieties (Table 1).

Supplying traditional cultivars to scientists and institutions inside India and abroad is an important activity of

the national center. About 5,000 varieties have been sent to scientists and institutions in 24 countries during the last decade. A few countries and institutions that have received large numbers of accessions, particularly from 1974 to 1977, are shown in Table 2. **W**

Newest rice varieties in 10 Asian nations

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

To determine the types of new rice varieties going out to farmers in Asia, IRRI surveyed rice breeders at 29 research centers in 10 countries on the varieties that had been released by their stations during the previous 5 years. The research project, initiated in 1975, was partially funded by a research grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.

Twenty-seven of the experiment stations had released 165 new varieties (two stations had not released any varieties during the time period). For all stations surveyed, the average number of released varieties was 5.7, or a little more than one new variety per year. For only the stations that had released varieties during the 5-year period, the average was 6.1 varieties/station.

Next, each breeder was asked how many of the new varieties had been bred locally (within his country) and how many had come from IRRI. Breeders were also asked to name the parents of locally bred varieties.

Seventy-eight percent of the 165 varieties had been bred in the countries where they were released; 22% were developed at IRRI (see figure).

Table 1. Present status of national gene bank at Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Source	Varieties (no.)			Total
	Early maturity	Medium maturity	Late maturity	
World collection (AC no.)	1,386	1,254	924	3,564
Jeypore Botanical Survey (JBS no.)	241	1,006	321	1,568
Manipur collection (MNP no.)	40	495	224	759
Assam Rice Collection (ARC no.)	447	4,874	207	5,528
Miscellaneous collection	550	1,155	350	2,055
New collection from states (NCS no., duration not yet classified)	—	—	—	1,431
Total	2,664	8,784	2,026	14,905

Table 2. Countries and institutions that have received major supplies of seed from the national gene bank, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Country	Varieties supplied (no.)				Total
	1974	1975	1976	1977	
IRRI (Philippines)	22	24	65	2,893	3,004
USSR	22	32	41	253 ^a	348
West Africa	28	34	69	8	139
Vietnam	—	41	9	—	50
USA	—	—	1	33	34
Liberia	—	35	—	—	35
Total	72	166	185	3,187	3,610

^a Includes material committed to be sent.